

VIKRAMORVASIYAM: REVOLVES AROUND A MORTAL'S LOVE FOR CELESTIAL MAIDEN

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Abstract

Kalidasa's play Vikramorvasiyam written in the 5th century CE. The plot revolves around a mortal's love for a celestial maiden. The drama has a well known crazy scene in which the king, bereaved, walks through a beautiful forest, apostrophizing various flowers and trees as they were his love. Vikramorvasiyam is a five-act drama written by Kalidasa that depicts the lover of Pururavasa, the king of Pratisthana, and Urvasi, a celestial nymph. Kalidasa appears to have focused on personality rather than narrative creation, as he did in the Malavikagnimitram. The most contentious section of the play, however, is Act IV, in which the hero, disturbed by separation, expresses his sentiments in brief, charming and tragic songs. It is not a long narrative or descriptive poetry that may be read with breaks or intervals. Kalidasa transforms this long-drawn sorrowful tragedy into a musical dance and he makes deft use of Prakrit appropriate for music as well as the lone state of the hero.

KeyWords:

Apostrophizing, Bereaved, Beautiful, Celestial, Charming, Continuous, Crazy, Focused, Musical, Tragedy

Introduction :

The story of Vikramorvasiyam (Urvasi won through Valor) is based on the traditional mythology of the mortal Pururavasas' love for the celestial lady Urvasi. The account appears in embryonic form in a Rig Vedic song and in a substantially expanded version in the Satapatha Brahmana. It depicts the love romance of earthly king Puruvas and celestial nymph Urvasi. As an immortal, she must return to the heavens, where an unlucky mishap sends her down to earth as a mortal with the curse that she will die, the moment her beloved sets eyes on the child she will bear him. The curse is removed after

ainto vine, and the lovers are permitted to live together on Earth. Vikramorvasiyam is the second of Kalidasa's three plays, the other two belong Abhijnanasakuntalam and Malavikagnimitram. The language used in Vikramorvasiyam exemplifies of the grace and beauty of Kalidasa's style.¹

According to one theory, Vikrama' in the title alludes to Kalidasa's patron king Vikramaditya. However, there is no conclusive evidence for this, although both are said to have lived around the same time period. It simply means valour. The classical theory of Sanskrit drama, known as Natyasastra makes it a rule that the plot of a Sanskrit drama, must be famous.² Accordingly, authors of Sanskrit plays use the stories from Puranas, Vedic texts and classic epics, namely Mahabharata and Ramayana for developing plays. However, the care objective of a drama is entertainment. Since every one is familiar with the basic plot, if the presentation of the play is not interesting or enchanting in same way, people would be bored. Hence there is emphasis an originally of the playwright. In the case of Vikramorvasiyam, here is how Kalidasa has adopted the original subject.³

In the 95th section, called Sukta of the tenth cluster, there is a dialogue between Pururava and Urvashi. Situation suggests that she has left the king after living for four years with him. The king beseeches her to return, but she refuses. The story ends that Satapatha Brahmana: Apparently aimed at emphasizing importance of a Yagnya, Pururava his city. She agreed with a condition, but when the king could not honor it because of manipulation by Gandharva people, she left him. Later, moved by the king's plight without her. She agreed to return once every year to him. The king still missed her a lot, so now convinced of his love. The Gandharvas asked him to perform a Yagnya, due to which Pururava attained Gandharava hood and could reunite with Urvashi. Puruana: Un all, Vishnu Purana, Padma Purana, Matsya Purana, Mahabharata, Bhagabata Purana and the story of Gunadhya in Brihatkatha are the source of the story of Prururava and Urvashi. There are multiple versions of these stories in different sources, but one can see the following elements in this pool: That Urvashi descended from heaven for some reason and met Pururava; the two lived together under some conditions for some time. At least on one occasion Urvashi had to part from the king under some sort of breach, for which she changed form, Urvashi returned to her form and got reunited with the king, but

there came a time when she had to return to the heaven to serve Indra. The two had a son together, named Ayush.⁴

Whether they lived together happily ever after is questionable, because there is one more story in Mahabharata, because there is one more story in Mahabharata in which Arjuna goes to heaven and meets Urvashi there. Hence, by inference, she and Pururava lived together during his life time, as he was a mortal.⁵ Adaptations by Kalidasa add novelty and surprise in the original subject, and infuse fresh depth and perspective. Urvashi, was banished from the heaven, but how she got that punishment is Kalidasa's own imagination. According to Vikramorvasiyam, she was playing the part of Laxmi in a play directed by Bharata Muni, performed in the court of Indra.⁶

In the scene of Laxmi Swayamvara, she was asked who she had given her heart to. Urvashi, smitten by Pururava at that time, could not distinguish between her role and herself, and ended up saying, Pururava instead of 'Purushottama'. This lack of mindfulness angered Bharata Muni, who cursed her to fall to earth. This curse, actually, was a boon for her, Indra, out of his appreciation for her, modified the curse by saying that she would return from earth when Pururava sees the face of their son.⁷

Some of the original versions suggest that Urvashi returned to heaven the moment her conditions were breached, without consideration for Pururava's repeated requests and his anguish at parting. However, Kalidasa adds the wonderful element of Sangama-hiya gem for reuniting Urvashi and Pururava with their son Ayush, and then adds visit by Narada carrying the message from Indra that since Pururava is a valued friend of his, and in future wars with demons his support is going to be pivotal, Urvashi could stay with him until end of his days. This addition of Indra's gesture at once depicts Urvashi's hesitation and pain to leave, desire to stay, being bound by the curse-all being eased by Indra's favour.⁸

Forest of Kartikeya where women were banned: Again, the original story mentions that the two were sent apart due to a curse, but Kalidasa adds the imagination that when the two went to mount Gandhamardana after their marriage, Pururava once started at a Gandharva girl named Udayavati, who was playing by the river.⁹ Enraged by jealousy or displeasure, Urvashi stormed out of that place- and went straight into a forest which was prohibited for women. Thus she turned into a vine. Pururava, moved to

extreme sixth stage of being in love, tried to find her and this is an opportunity Kalidasa created to add narration of Nature, and conversation of Pururava with various elements of nature, flora and fauna. Description of nature is Kalidasa's forte and the metaphors he uses to describe his beloved are wonderful.¹⁰

Urvashi's dilemma- Kalidasa adds complexity confronting the character of Urvashi by introducing the condition that when Pururava sees the face of their son, Urvashi will return to the heaven. In Vikramorvashiyam, Urvashi conceives and delivers the son quickly without the knowledge of Pururava who never saw her pregnant. Son is placed under the care of Chyavan Rishi, who makes sure that since he is a Khatriya, he would be taught Dhanurveda along with other systems of knowledge, but he will abide by the rules of the Ashram. The day Ayush breaks the code of non-violence by hunting a bird who carried a red gem, is also the day when Pururava's cherished Sangamaniya gem is picked up by a bird who believed it to be a piece of red meat. Some one brings to the king the dead bird with the gem and the arrow that hit the bird. Chyavana rishi sends back Ayush to Pururava's court. King reads the inscription on the arrow, which says that it belonged to " Ayush, the son of Ila's son and Urvashi". Urvashi tells the whole story of curse to Pururava who is very happy that his bane of being childless is removed, who appoints Ayush as the prince and is very unhappy that Urvashi would now have to leave. At that point Narada brings the happy tidings and the play ends.¹¹

Major characters appearing in the play are: Pururava: A king of the lunar dynasty, who rules Pratihsthana kingdom, the hero of the play. Urvashi: the foremost of the apsaras, the celestial dancers of the heavens, the heroine of the play. Ayus: son of Pururava and Urvashi, fostered in the hermitage of sage Chyavana. Chitrlekha: An apasaras and Urvashi's close friend. Manavaka: A vidushaka (jester) and Pururava's close friend, who aids in his romantic pursuit. Aushinari: The princess of Kashi and the queen consort of Pururava. Nipunika: The personal attendant of Aushinari, who informs the queen about Pururava's love for Urvashi. Rambha, Menaka and Sahajanya: Three Apsara companions of Urvashi, who report about her abduction to Pururavas. Narada- A divine-sage, who acts as emissary of Indra. Chitraratha: Chief of Gandharavas, the heavenly musician, and the messenger of the god Indra. Pallava and Glava: Disciples of Bharatha Muni, Satyavati: A disciple of Chyavana and the foster mother of Ayus. Suta:

Charioteer of Pururavas. Latavya- Chief officer of royal chambers of Aushinari. Kitata- A huntress dwelling in the mountains. Yavani, a Graeco- Bacterial bow-bearer.¹²

The king of the gods and an ally of Pururava. Bharata Muni: The sage who curses Urvashi to descend on the Earth. Keshi: A danava monarch who abducts Urvashi. Brihaspati- the teacher of the gods. Kubera: God of riches Kartikeya- the commander of the god's army and the protagonist of Kumarsambhavam, another work by Kalidasa. Udayavati: A Gandharva girl to whom Pururava is temporarily attracted. Chyavana- the teacher of Ayus. Dikpalas: the divine guardians of the directions.¹³

Vikramorvasiyam is the second of Kalidasa's three dramas, the first being Malavikagnimitram and the third being the well known Abhijnanasakuntalam. Vikramorvasiyam, a drama authored by Kalidasa in the fifth century CE. The narrative centers around the love of a mortal for celestial beauty, Kalidasa appears to have focuses on personality rather than plot building in this play, as he did in the Malavikagnimitram. Thus Vikramorvasiyam is a five act Sanskrit play by ancient Indian poet Kalidasa, who live in the 4th or 5th century CE, on the Vedic love story of king Pururavas and an Apsara (nymph) named Urvashi known for her beauty. The legend occurs in embryonic form in a hymn of the Rig Veda and in a much amplified version in the Shatapatha- Brahman.¹⁴ It tells the story of mortal king Pururavas and celestial nymph Urvashi who falls in love. As an immortal, she has to return to the heavens, where an unfortunate accident causes her to be sent back to the earth as a mortal with the curse that she will die (and thus return to heaven) the moment her lover lays his eyes on the child which she will bear him. After a series of mishaps, including Urvashi's temporary transformation into a vine, the curse is lifted, and the lovers are allowed to remain together on the earth. The language employed in Vikramorvasiyam displays all the elegance and the beauties of Kalidasa's style.

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